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The impact of specific environmentally friendly resistances on the barley powdery mildew disease under the effects of Climate Change

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Abstract—The aim of this study to evaluate the efficacy of eco-friendly treatments *i.e.* biocide Blight stop, three natural oil extracts—neem oil, thyme oil and tea tree oil—as well as fungicide Farmazole in reducing powdery mildew infection on the susceptible Egyptian barley varieties were carried out under field experiments conducted at Giza Experimental Station, Agricultural Research Centre (ARC), during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons. All eco-friendly treatments and fungicide reduced diseases severity%, area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) and average coefficient of infection (ACI) compared to the control treatment in the two seasons, in addition increase the yield, total chlorophyll and carotenoids in comparison with control treatment. Spraying fungicide Farmazole provided the most effective treatments, followed by biocide-Blight stop. On the opposite, thyme oil was recorded the least effectiveness compared with control treatment during the two growing seasons 2024 and 2025.

Keywords: *Barley, powdery mildew, Biological control, neem oil, tea tree*

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INTRODUCTION

The main crop in Egypt that is widely grown in the North Coastal Region and the newly reclaimed areas with saline soils and little fresh water is barley. Barley is one of the most important cereal crops in the world (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). Malcolmson et al. (2005) state that it is utilized for the feeding of both humans and animals.

Blumeria graminis f. sp. *hordei* is a biotrophic fungus that causes powdery mildew, the most dangerous barley disease (Tratwal and Bocianowski 2014 and Abdullaev et al., 2021). In humid, fairly temperate areas, powdery mildew can cause a loss of production of up to 30%, with an average loss of 5–10% (Agostinetto et al., 2014). Fungicides are usually used to treat barley powdery mildew in order to control plant diseases. However, the usage of fungicides is frequently rendered ineffective over time due to the establishment of fungicide-resistant pathogenic strains and their detrimental consequences on both human health and the environment (Hafez and El-Baghdady, 2013)

The overall concept is to use the methods that, at a given stage of the development of the farmed plant, are the most efficient and least detrimental to the environment. According to the theory of evolutionary plant cultivation, one of the relatively easy and affordable methods that improves the long-term viability of genetic resistance is the cultivation of modern cultivars in a wide variety of combinations and complex hybridized groups (Newton et al., 2009 & 2010 and Matyjaszczyk 2015).

Barley leaves treated with 0.5% neem oil (*Azadirachta indica*), Thyme Oil (*Thymus vulgaris*), and Tea Tree Oil (*Melaleuca alternifolia*) experienced a

significant decrease in the severity of barley powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei*), from 63.4% (comparison group) to 9.4% (BSO), 16% neem oil), and 16.4% (tea tree oil) when compared to the control treatment. It is evident that oils' ability to protect against powdery mildew is primarily due to their ability to inhibit the germination of conidia and reduce the growth of pathogenic fungi. Thymoquinone, the main ingredient in essential oils and the fixed oil, only slightly activates host defense mechanisms (Ali and Blunden, 2003).

Therefore, it is important to pay more attention to BSO and other oils that are effective against the microorganisms that cause powdery mildew as safe and adequate alternative control measures for the production of healthy and organic foods (Hafez *et al.*, 2014).

The treatment of pepper plants with Blight stop at the rate of 1 L:50 L water recorded the highest percentage of decrease in disease incidence and severity of pepper plants, and also recorded the highest increase in vegetative growth, yield, fruit quality such and total chlorophyll during the two growing seasons 2024 and 2025 compared with control treatment (Ahmed *et al.*, 2021).

It is feasible to employ unconventional biological agents, including *Trichoderma asperillum* 34, a commercially available biological product, as a substitute for fungicides in addressing the symptoms of net blotch disease in barley. Furthermore, the treatments proved effective as they significantly enhanced the yield attributes in comparison to the control group (Hafez et al., 2019).

The aim of this study to reduce the use of chemical fungicides for controlling barley powdery mildew, produce barley grains of high quality and quantity without any toxicity at the food chain, and sustain

sustainable development over time, and examine the effects of some environmentally friendly materials, such as plant extract oils and biological control.

METHODOLOGY

1. Barley genotypes

Barley genotypes, whose names and pedigrees are listed in Table 1, were kindly provided by the Barley Research Department of the Field Crops Research Institute, Agricultural Research Centre in Egypt. These genotypes were used in both greenhouse and field studies.

Table 1. Name and pedigree of two barley genotypes employed in greenhouse and field experiments during two seasons 2024 and 2025.

No	Cultivar Name	Pedigree
1	Giza 132	Rihane-05//AS 46/Aths*2Athe/Lignee 686
2	Giza 123	Giza 117/FAO 86

2. Compounds used to treat powdery mildew on barley plants:

In this study, Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts—neem oils, thyme and tee tree oil—as well as Farmazole as a chemical pesticide were

applied on barley plants to study their effectiveness against barley mildew disease caused by *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* throughout the trial seasons of 2024 and 2025, as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Technical data sheet of compounds used to treat powdery mildew on barley plants during two successive seasons, 2024 and 2025.

Ser.	Trade name	Active ingredient	Recommended dose	Source
1	Farmzol	25% EC Propiconazole	15 ml/100 Lit	BASF Egypt for Agricultural Solutions, New Cairo, Egypt.
2	Blight Stop	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> 30x10 ⁶ spore/ml	1 Lit./100 Lit	Biological Control Production Unit Central Lab. of Organic Agriculture, CLOA; ARC, Egypt
3	neem oil	Azadirachtin, Nimbin	20 ml/l	Harraz for Food Industry & Natural Products
4	Thyme oil	40.5% Thymol, 23.6% P-cymen, 3.2% Carvacrol, 5.4% Inalool, 2.6% B-caryphllene and Terpinen	20 ml/l	Harraz for Food Industry & Natural Products
5	Tea Tree Oil	Terpinen-4-ol	20 ml/l	Harraz for Food Industry & Natural Products

3. Greenhouse experiments:

3.1. Samples of diseases and barley powdery mildew isolates:

In accordance with the methods outlined by Xu et al. (2014), infected barley leaves were collected from the spreading lines within the disease nurseries. Subsequently, a single-colony isolate of *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* (Bgh) was generated and preserved on seedlings of the barley variety, utilizing test tubes with a diameter of 5 cm filled with sterile soil

3.2. Spore Processing:

Conidia of each isolate from the aforementioned seedlings were placed onto the barley seedlings of Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132, which were grown in pots with 400 mL of sterilised soil, and then incubated in a growth chamber at $20\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ with continuous lighting to multiply the Bgh isolates. Five layers of cheesecloth were placed on the surface of a glass cylinder with a 10 cm diameter to completely enclose the seedlings and avoid cross-contamination. After 3-5 days of white mycelia's emergence, leaf segments of 5 cm in length from the inoculated leaves were cut off, placed upside-down on 1% agar plates, and cultivated at $18\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ under a 16/8 h (light/dark) lighting regime. The conidia were collected onto tissue paper in the laminar flow after 5-7 days of incubation and put into 2.0 mL centrifuge tubes. The pathogenicity assay was conducted using fresh conidia (Wang *et al.*, 2022).

3.3. Typing In Virulence:

In the climate-controlled greenhouse of the Barley Diseases Research

Department, barley grains of the varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 were grown in clay pots with a diameter of 30 cm for eight days. The most prevalent races of *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* were artificially inoculated into each pot at the 2-leaf stage by carefully shaking the sporulation leaf segments while the plants were grown in a greenhouse at a temperature of 20°C (Nair and Ellingba, 1962). Twenty-four hours after inoculation, leaves were sprayed with the recommended doses of the aforementioned Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts—neem oils, thyme and eucalyptus oils—as well as, Farmazole as a chemical pesticide. Plants were strictly sprayed with distilled water only as a control treatment. Three replicates of each treatment were used in the experiment, which was conducted using a completely randomized block design.

In addition, cultural practices and irrigation were applied. According to Jensen *et al.* (1992), the infection types (ITs) of each barley variety collected from different Bgh isolates were graded on a scale of 0 to 4, and responses for resistance/susceptibility were determined as follows: 0-2 for resistant (R) and 3-4 for susceptible (S). Incubation period (IP) was calculated as the number of days between the inoculation and the first sign of the disease's initial symptoms or signs, such as spots. (Holliday, 2001). Latent period was calculated as the number of days between the day of inoculation and the day when 50% of the conidia emerged and damaged the leaf epidermal (Andres, 1982).

• Disease severity:

According to the equation which described by Ahmed *et al.*, 2021, disease intensity was assessed by examining the leaves from each treatment at random, using a 0 – 4 scale, where 0=no disease; 1=1–10% leaf area affected; 2=11 – 25% leaf area affected, 3=26 – 50% leaf area affected and

4≥50% leaf area affected. The percentage disease index was calculated by using the formula:

$$DSI = \frac{\sum (v \times n)}{Z \times N} \times 100$$

Where:

D.S.I= Disease severity index, n = Number of leaves in each category, v = Numerical value of each category, Z= Numerical value of highest category and N = Total number of leaves in the sample.

$$\text{Reduction in disease severity \%} = \frac{\text{Control}-T_i}{\text{Cont}}$$

4. Filed experiments condition (adult stage):

To assess the efficacy of Blight-stop as a biocide, field experiments were carried out at the Giza Experimental Station, Agricultural Research Centre (ARC) during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons. The study involved three natural oil extracts—neem oil, thyme oil, and eucalyptus oil—alongside Farmazole, a chemical pesticide, to combat natural infections of powdery mildew on susceptible Egyptian barley varieties. The seeds Giza 123 and Giza 132 were examined using a randomized complete block design with three replicate plots, each measuring 11.10 m² (3 × 3.5 m), with a spacing of 20 cm between rows. In line with the guidelines set forth by the Ministry of Agriculture, all traditional cultural practices were executed at the designated times. Each of the aforementioned foliar spray treatments was applied separately at the recommended doses, with the first application occurring at the heading stage (70 days post-planting) coinciding with the onset of infection, and the second application taking place 10 days later. Disease severity was subsequently recorded.

Disease assessment under field conditions:

In each trial, ten plants at heading stage from each treatment were assessed visually on a 0–10 scale for the percentage of leaf area covered by powdery mildew (Large, 2007). Disease scores were converted for analysis by Hafez *et al.*, 2014 *i.e.* 0 = 0 %, 1 = 0–3 %, 2 = +3–6 %, 3 = +6–12 %, 4 = +12–25 %, 5 = +25–50 %, 6 = +50–75 %, 7 = +75–88 %, 8 = +88–94 %, 9 = +94–97 % and 10 = +97–100 %. Disease severity index (DSI) was calculated using the following formula:

$$DSI = \frac{\sum \text{Ratings of each plant}}{10 \times \text{Number of plants rated}} \times 100$$

Area under disease progress curve (AUDPC):

The (AUDPC) was calculated using a simple formula adopted by (Pandy *et al.*, 1989) as follow:

$$AUDPC = D [\frac{1}{2} (Y_1 + Y_K) + (Y_2 + Y_3 + \dots + Y_{K-1})]$$

Whereas, D= days between two consecutive (time intervals)

Y₁+ Y_K=sum of the first and last disease scores
Y₂+ Y₃+ + Y_{K-1} = sum of all in between disease scores.

Yield components:

All harvested plants at maturity stage during the two growing seasons 2024 and 2025 at Giza station and plots were recorded in terms of biological yield (kg/plot). Following harvesting, the grain yield (kg/plot) was calculated from the harvested plants' or plots' collected grains. The mean weight of 1000-grain samples collected at random was used to calculate the 1000-grain weight (g). The increase over control in yield component was estimated according to the equation adopted by Ahmed (2013) and Hafez *et al.*, (2014) as follow:-

$$\text{Increase over control \%} = \frac{\text{Treatment}-\text{Control}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Estimating the amount of chlorophyll and carotenoids

The technique of Litchenthaler (1987) and Yu *et al.* (2014) was used to determine the total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g).

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis software SAS was used to analyse the data. All multiple analysis was initially evaluated through an analysis of variance (ANOVA) comparison of means, the least significant differences (LSD) AT P = 0.05, and Duncan's multiple range test (Duncan, 1995) was used to determine the results.

RESULTS

Using the Giza 132 and Giza 123 barley varieties, this study assessed the efficacy of Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts (Neem oil, thyme, and Tea tree oil), and Farmazole as a chemical pesticide with the recommended dosages listed above at table 2 against barley mildew disease caused by *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* in both the greenhouse and field trials.

Greenhouse studies:

Table 3. Effect of some eco-friendly treatments and fungicide as foliar spray on disease severity % of inoculated barley seedling varieties Giza123 and Giza132 with *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* under greenhouse condition.

Different treatments	Concentration	Barley cultivars			
		Giza 123		Giza 132	
		Disease severity %	Reduction %	Disease severity %	Reduction %
Blight stop	1Lit/100L	10.00	87.36	10.00	88.24
Neem oil	20ml/L	13.00	85.06	15.00	82.35
Tea tree oil	20ml/L	18.00	79.31	20.00	76.47
Thyme oil	20ml/L	27.00	67.82	31.00	65.71
Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	00.00	100.00	00.00	100.00
Untreated	Only water	87.00	0.00	85.00	0.00
LSD at 5%		2.12		2.11	

Effect of some eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on disease severity:

According to data in table 3, spraying different environmentally friendly treatments, such as Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts—neem oils, thyme, and eucalyptus oils—and Farmazole fungicide, significantly decreased the percentages of disease severity in inoculated barley seedling varieties Giza123 and Giza132 with *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* under greenhouse conditions as compared to control treatment. The disease severity of powdery mildew on both the Giza123 and Giza132 types is totally controlled by the foliar application of farmazole fungicide, contrary to other eco-friendly treatments.

Blight stop as biocide caused the highest efficacy in reduction (87.36 and 88.24%) followed by neem oils oil (85.06 and 82.35%) of disease severity of powdery mildew on Giza123 and Giza132 barley varieties, respectively compared with other oils rather than control treatment. On the other hand thyme oil caused the least effect one. Finally, Giza123 barley variety higher sensitive for infection with powdery mildew than Giza132 during greenhouse conditions.

Effect of some eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on incubation and latent periods (day) of barley powdery mildew:

Powdery mildew infection of two barley varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132, expressed as incubation period (IP) and latent period (LP) were affected differently after spraying primary leaves of barley seeds with the tested ecofriendly and Optus fungicide treatments in comparison with control treatment.

The foliar spraying of barley seedlings with Blight-stop compounds as a biocide, three natural oil extracts (neem oils, thyme, and eucalyptus oils), and the fungicide Farmazole showed their efficacy in lengthening the incubation period (IP) and the latent period (LP), which increased their effectiveness in decreasing the severity of infection with the barley powdery mildew, *Blumeria graminis* f. f.sp. *hordei*, as seen at the previous (Table 3), compared to the control treatment.

In this regard, the fungicide Farmazole demonstrated a significant increase in the lengthening of the incubation period (IP) of 76.47% and the latent period (LP) of 40.00% for the barley powdery mildew *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* when compared to other natural oil extracts. Thyme oil extract, on the other hand, showed the least significant increase one.

Filed experiments:

The effect of ecofriendly treatment on barley powdery mildew during 2024 and 2025 growing seasons.

This investigation evaluated the efficacy of Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts—black seeds, thyme, and eucalyptus oils—as well as Farmazole as a chemical pesticide with recommended doses as mentioned above at table 2 on powdery mildew of Giza 132 and Giza Giza 123 barley varieties under field trials during 2024 and 2025 growing seasons.

The efficiency of foliar spraying with tested ecofriendly and fungicide treatments were used to assess the barley powdery mildew infection, which was expressed as average percentages of mildewed leaf area (PM disease severity%), area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC), and average coefficient of infection (ACI).

The obtained results in Tables 5.a and 5.b indicated that all environmentally friendly and fungicide treatments are highly effective in reducing the severity of the barley powdery mildew disease, the average coefficient of infection (ACI), and the area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) when compared to control treatments on both barley variety, Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132, during two successive seasons, 2024 and 2025.

Table 4. Effect of different eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on incubation and latent periods (day) of inoculated barley seedling varieties Giza123 and Giza2000 with *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* under greenhouse condition.

Barley varieties	Different treatments	Concentration	Disease severity %			
			Incubation period (day)	Increase %	Latent periods (day)	Increase %
Giza Giza 123	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	9.75	72.26	11.25	36.36
	Neem oil	20ml/L	8.44	49.12	10.42	26.30
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	7.23	27.74	9.25	12.12
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	6.98	23.32	9.00	9.09
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	10.00	76.68	11.55	40.00
Control	Untreated	Only water	5.66	0.00	8.25	0.00

LSD at 5%			0.92		1.18	
Giza 132	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	9.65	84.87	10.83	35.21
	Neem oil	20ml/L	8.12	55.56	10.02	25.09
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	7.10	36.02	9.12	13.86
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	6.21	18.97	8.22	2.62
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	10.00	91.57	11.55	44.19
Control	Untreated	Only water	5.22	0.00	8.01	0.00
LSD at 5%			0.91		1.01	

On the barley cultivars Giza Giza 123 and Brief 2000, during the two subsequent seasons of 2024 and 2021, the fungicide Farmazole superior to control treatments in regards to effectiveness in reducing the severity of powdery mildew disease, the average infection coefficient (ACI), and the area under the disease progression curve (AUDPC). Blight stop was the next most

effective treatment. On the other hand, the therapy that involved spraying barley plants with an extract of thyme oil was the least effective. The results show that throughout the two research seasons, cultivar Giza Giza 123 of barley was more susceptible to the powdery mildew disease than cultivar Giza 132.

Table 5.a. Effect of spraying different eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on disease severity%, average coefficient of infection (ACI) and area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) of *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* on barley varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 under field conditions during growing season 2024.

Barley varieties	Different treatments	Concentration	Disease severity %	Reduction %	ACI	Reduction %	AUDPC	Reduction %
Giza Giza 123	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	10.22	87.74	3.57	95.22	52.50	89.30
	Neem oil	20ml/L	15.60	81.28	4.17	94.41	86.60	82.36
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	20.45	75.46	10.17	86.38	96.13	80.41
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	22.76	72.69	11.50	84.59	113.8	76.81
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	09.83	88.21	3.41	95.44	51.29	89.55
Control	Untreated	Only water	83.35	0.00	74.65	0.00	490.8	0.00
LSD at 5%			1.12		0.88		2.65	
Giza 132	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	10.12	87.83	3.52	95.20	52.20	89.14
	Neem oil	20ml/L	14.5	82.56	4.15	94.34	85.40	82.24
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	20.22	75.68	10.16	86.15	95.70	80.09
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	21.85	73.72	11.45	84.39	112.80	76.54
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	9.33	88.78	3.40	95.36	51.10	89.37
Control	Untreated	Only water	83.15	0.00	73.35	0.00	480.75	0.00
LSD at 5%			0.98		0.86		2.64	

Table 5.b. Effect of spraying different eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on disease severity%, average coefficient of infection (ACI) and area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) of *Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *hordei* on barley varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 under field conditions during growing season 2025.

Barley varieties	Different treatments	Concentration	Disease severity %	Reduction %	ACI	Reduction %	AUDPC	Reduction %
Giza Giza 123	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	9.44	88.63	3.50	95.22	52.10	89.05
	Neem oil	20ml/L	14.45	82.60	4.14	94.35	85.35	82.06
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	20.12	75.77	10.00	86.35	95.55	79.91

	Thyme oil	20ml/L	21.33	74.32	11.33	84.53	112.78	76.29
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ /L	9.22	88.90	3.20	95.63	51.00	89.28
Control	Untreated	Only water	83.05	0.00	73.25	0.00	475.63	0.00
	LSD at 5%		1.10		0.76		2.62	
	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	9.35	88.71	3.45	95.28	51.89	89.09
	Neem oil	20ml/L	14.23	82.82	4.22	94.22	85.16	82.10
Giza 132	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	20.1	75.74	9.70	86.72	95.33	79.96
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	21.22	74.39	11.18	84.70	112.47	76.35
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ /L	9.10	89.02	3.12	95.73	51.28	89.22
Control	Untreated	Only water	82.85	0.00	73.05	0.00	475.63	0.00
	LSD at 5%		0.96		0.74		2.61	

The yield components:

All environmentally friendly treatments, namely Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts - neem oil, thyme, and tea tree oil, and the chemical pesticide Farmazole, when sprayed at the recommended concentrations in Table 2 on barley plants of Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132, resulted in a decrease in the severity of infection and the development of powdery mildew disease, as well as an increase in the weight of a thousand grains (g) and an increase in grain yield / plot (kg) compared to the control treatment during the growing seasons 2024 and 2025.

In addition to spraying the plants with the fungicide Farmazole, the highest reading in the weight of 1000 grains (g) and the increase in grain yield / plot (kg) for the two barley cultivars were recorded, followed by an increase in the productivity of the biocide Blight-stop compared to the control treatment during the two study seasons. On the contrary, the thyme oil extract treatment was the least effective.

The obtained data in Table 7, indicate that all ecofriendly treatments *i.e.* Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts - black seeds, thyme, and eucalyptus oils, and the fungal pesticide Farmazole, when sprayed at the recommended concentrations in Table 2 on barley plants of Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132, increased total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g) as estimated the photosynthetic pigments in comparison with untreated plants during the growing seasons 2024 and 2025. The fungicide Farmazole provided the highest level of total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g) in the majority of cases, followed by biocide-Blight stop. In contrast, thyme oil was the smallest effectiveness. The results showed that throughout the two research seasons, cultivar Giza Giza 123 of barley was more susceptible to the powdery mildew disease and recorded in total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g) less than cultivar Giza 132.

Table 6.a. Effect of spraying different eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on 1000 kernel weight (g) of barley varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 under field conditions during growing two seasons 2024 and 2025.

Barley varieties	Different treatments	Concentration	2024 growing season		2021/2022 growing season	
			1000 grain weight (g)	Increasing %	1000 grain weight (g)	Increasing %
Giza Giza 123	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	55.15	23.38	55.30	23.30
	Neem oil	20ml/L	54.31	21.50	54.42	21.34
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	53.14	18.88	53.51	19.31

	Thyme oil	20ml/L	51.66	15.57	51.85	15.61
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	56.05	25.39	56.10	25.08
Control	Untreated	Only water	44.70	0.00	44.85	0.00
	LSD at 5%		0.42		0.52	
	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	55.25	22.51	55.60	22.98
	Neem oil	20ml/L	54.52	20.89	54.77	21.15
Giza 132	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	53.52	18.67	53.92	19.27
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	52.03	15.37	52.38	15.86
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	57.10	26.61	57.20	26.52
Control	Untreated	Only water	45.10	0.00	45.21	0.00
	LSD at 5%		0.40		0.51	

Table 6.b.Effect of spraying different eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on green yield/plot (Kg) of barley varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 under field conditions during growing two seasons 2024 and 2025.

Barley varieties	Different treatments	Concentration	2024 growing season		2021/2022 growing season	
			Grain yield / plot (kg)	Increasing %	Grain yield / plot (kg)	Increasing %
Giza Giza 123	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	5.15	25.00	5.18	23.63
	Neem oil	20ml/L	4.92	19.42	4.96	18.38
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	4.81	16.75	4.83	15.27
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	4.64	12.62	4.70	12.17
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	5.23	26.94	5.25	25.30
Control	Untreated	Only water	4.12	0.00	4.19	0.00
	LSD at 5%		1.10		0.76	
Giza 132	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	5.16	22.86	5.18	22.75
	Neem oils oil	20ml/L	4.98	18.57	5.02	18.96
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	4.84	15.24	4.87	15.40
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	4.77	13.57	4.80	13.74
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	5.24	24.76	5.26	24.64
Control	Untreated	Only water	4.20	0.00	4.22	0.00
	LSD at 5%		0.96		0.74	

Table 7. Effect of spraying different eco-friendly treatments and fungicide on total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g) of barley varieties Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 under field conditions during growing two seasons 2024 and 2025.

Barley varieties	Different treatments	Concentration	2024 growing season			2021/2022 growing season		
			Total chlorophyll (mg/g)		Carotenoids (mg/g)	Total chlorophyll (mg/g)		Carotenoids (mg/g)
			a	b		a	b	
Giza Giza 123	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	3.1	3.0	2.9	3.2	3.1	3.0
	Neem oil	20ml/L	2.6	2.5	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.5
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.4	2.3	2.1
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	1.7	1.6	1.5	1.7	1.6	2.0
	Farmazole	0.15 cm ³ / L	3.2	3.1	3.0	3.3	3.2	3.1
Control	Untreated	Only water	1.3	1.2	0.9	1.3	1.0	1.1

LSD at 5%			0.42	0.24	0.23	0.22	0.27	0.25
Giza 132	Blight stop	1Lit/100L	3.3	3.2	3.0	3.4	3.3	3.1
	Neem oil	20ml/L	2.7	2.6	2.5	2.8	2.7	2.5
	Tea tree oil	20ml/L	2.4	2.3	2.2	2.5	2.4	2.3
	Thyme oil	20ml/L	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.9	1.8	1.7
	Farmazole	0.15 cm³/ L	3.4	3.3	3.1	3.6	3.5	3.3
Control	Untreated	Only water	1.3	1.2	1.0	1.4	1.3	1.2
LSD at 5%			0.40	0.32	0.30	0.28	0.33	0.31

DISCUSSION

The primary focus of this research is to employ the most effective and least environmentally damaging techniques during a specific phase of the cultivated plant's growth. The use of eco-friendly materials as alternatives to non-chemical control methods, such as plant extract oils and biological control, aims to reduce the reliance on chemical fungicides for managing barley powdery mildew. This approach seeks to produce barley grains of high quality and quantity without introducing toxicity into the food chain, enhancing soil fertility, preserving environmental cleanliness, and ensuring sustainable development in the long term (Newton et al., 2009 & 2010 and Matyjaszczyk 2015).

The results obtained indicate that the use of biocides and plant oils as chemical inducers can serve as a safe and cost-effective approach to managing powdery mildew disease in barley plants. Cultivating barley as a mixed variety represents a concept of sustainable agriculture, which is based on the premise that plant protection should be economically viable, environmentally friendly, and socially accepted. In this context, modern plant protection systems should integrate all available methods for fungal control. Specifically, the application of eco-friendly treatments such as Blight Stop, , Neem oil is rich in bioactive compounds like **azadirachtin**, **nimbin**, and **quercetin**,

which contribute to its pesticidal and antimicrobial properties and has shown efficacy against fungal pathogens by disrupting spore germination and hyphal growth. Azadirachtin interferes with fungal hormone systems, reducing feeding and reproduction and Neem oil is biodegradable and considered safe for non-target organisms, making it suitable for eco-friendly agriculture.

Thyme oil contains potent compounds such as **thymol**, **carvacrol**, and **p-cymene**, which exhibit strong antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. Thymol and carvacrol disrupt fungal cell membranes, leading to leakage of cellular contents and death Effective against a range of pathogens including powdery mildew fungi. Combining thyme oil with other oils or biocontrol agents may enhance efficacy. (Evros vellios *et al.* 2023).

Tea tree oil is composed primarily of **terpinen-4-ol**, **γ -terpinene**, and **α -terpineol**, known for antimicrobial and antifungal activities. Terpinen-4-ol disrupts fungal cell walls and inhibits spore germination. Studies show tea tree oil can reduce fungal infections in barley including powdery mildew, when applied as foliar sprays through two spray applications for the management of barley powdery mildew was compared to the traditional systemic fungicide Farmazole on barley seedlings of the Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132 varieties under greenhouse conditions. Blight Stop (*Trichoderma harzianum*), when applied as a foliar spray at a concentration of 10ml/1L,

proved to be the most effective in controlling barley powdery mildew, followed by black seed oil. Conversely, thyme oil at a concentration of 20ml/L exhibited the least effectiveness compared to the other treatments. The potential of *Trichoderma* spp. in managing plant pathogenic fungi is well-documented, including their direct effects on target fungi through mechanisms such as competition, mycoparasitism, and antibiosis (Ahmed 2018).

Despite the fact that all the compounds tested significantly reduced the area affected by mildew, exhibiting varying levels of disease severity percentage, they also extended both the incubation and latent periods, which are regarded as the primary elements of partial resistance (Wilson, 1994). Essential oils contain abundant bioactive substances, including antimicrobial agents, which contribute to the aroma and flavor profiles. These compounds are recognized as highly effective inhibitors of microbial growth and demonstrate strong activity upon direct contact with pathogens (Ahmed, 2013).

To put it another way the foliar spray of Farmazole (Epoconazole) which is among the systemic fungicides under greenhouse conditions it is shown that the disease was completely checked compared to others.

Field application to evaluate the effectiveness of Blight-stop as a biocide, three natural oil extracts—neem, thyme and tea tree oils—as well as Farmazole as a chemical pesticide treatments against the natural infection with powdery mildew on the susceptible Egyptian barley varieties, field experiments were conducted at Giza Experimental Station, Agricultural Research Centre (ARC), during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons.

The analysis of the data obtained over the two seasons demonstrated that the application of various eco-friendly

treatments and fungicides led to a notable decrease in disease severity percentage, area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC), and average coefficient of infection (ACI) when compared to the control treatment. The most significant reduction was observed with the farmazole fungicide, followed by the Blight Stop biocide, while thyme oil provided the least disease protection in comparison to the other treatments..

While the eco-friendly treatments demonstrated lower efficacy in managing powdery mildew disease compared to the fungicides examined in this study, they are less persistent, making them safer for the environment and human health than fungicides. Consequently, it is crucial to focus more on basil and other oils that effectively combat the microorganisms responsible for powdery mildew, as they serve as safe and suitable alternative control methods for producing healthy and organic foods (Hafez et al., 2014).

Considering the routine and extensive use of these fungicides, they leave chemical residues in soil, water, and grains (Singh et al. 1994), which may subsequently impact both animal and human health (Kuc, 1991). The significant accumulation of residues has rendered fungicide pollution a global environmental issue, and it has been identified as highly toxic to aquatic organisms (Haque and Oine, 2019).

The management of powdery mildew in this study resulted in a significant enhancement of the grain yield components in the treated barley varieties (Giza Giza 123 and Giza 132), demonstrating a direct correlation between disease infection and yield (Narelle and Piotr, 2021). Furthermore, the treatments proved effective as they significantly improved the yield characteristics in comparison to the control group (Hafez et al., 2019).

The data presented in this study indicate that all eco-friendly treatments and the fungal

pesticide enhanced total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g), as assessed by the photosynthetic pigments, when compared to untreated plants during the growing seasons of 2024 and 2025. The fungicide Farmazole demonstrated the highest levels of total chlorophyll and carotenoids (mg/g) in most instances, followed by biocide-Blight stop. Conversely, thyme oil exhibited the least effectiveness.

This increase may result from the stimulation of pigment formation, which enhances the effectiveness of the photosynthetic apparatus, alongside a reduction in the rate of photophosphorylation that typically follows an infection, thereby improving disease resistance potential (Keutgen and Roeb, 1996). Furthermore, the use of certain natural treatments has been shown to elevate potassium levels, potentially leading to an increase in the number of chloroplasts per cell or activating the synthesis of carotenoids that safeguard chlorophyll from oxidation..

CONCLUSION

Field experiments were conducted at the Agricultural Research Centre (ARC)'s Giza Experimental Station during the 2024 and 2025 growing seasons with the objective to assess the efficacy of environmentally friendly treatments, such as the fungicide Farmazole, three natural oil extracts (Neem, Thyme, and Teatree oil), and the biocide Blight Stop, in reducing powdery mildew infection on the susceptible Egyptian barley varieties. In comparison to the control treatment, all environmentally friendly treatments and fungicides decreased the percentage of diseases which were severe, the area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC), and the average coefficient of infection (ACI) over the course of the two

seasons. They also increased yield, total chlorophyll, and carotenoids.

Author contribution

Majority contribution for the whole article belongs to the author. The author read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing interests

The author declares that he has no competing interests.

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